

Bibliometrics applied in STEM scientific research: contribution and impact through bibliometric analysis

Patricio Cortes-Rodríguez^{1,2}, Gloria Rojas-Díaz¹, Ricardo Vilches-Vargas¹

¹Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Sistema de Bibliotecas UC, Av. Vicuña Mackenna 4860, Santiago, Chile.

²pacortesr@uc.cl

The objective of this study is to determine with a bibliometric analysis, the contribution and impact of STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) scientific publications that employ bibliometric techniques as part of their investigative methodology. This, given that in recent years the contribution of this technique has been recognized, by providing strategic information for complex decision-making around research evaluation and management.

Methodology

First, a systematic analysis with the PRISMA protocol was carried out on citable publications from 2010 to 2019 that met the following criteria:

- With indexing in Web of Science (SCIE, SSCI and/or A&HCI)
- Article, Review or Proceedings Paper
- With classification in some of the 19 ESI (Essential Science Indicators) disciplines related to STEM (<http://help.producing.com/inCites2Live/8300-TRS.html>)
- Whose titles, abstract and/or full text are related to the studies subject

Subsequently the dataset of 1,962 papers was analyzed with the bibliometric tools InCites (Clarivate Analytics) and VOSviewer (CWTS) providing pertinent information to the questions posed in the study.

Results

1) How many STEM scientific investigations that include bibliometric analysis are published annually? What is the impact of these publications?

2) Which ESI disciplines related to STEM, mostly use bibliometric analysis?

ESI disciplines (STEM)	Nº papers
Clinical Medicine	703
Environment/Ecology	320
Engineering	262
Psychiatry/Psychology	118
Neuroscience & Behavior	89
Computer Science	70
Chemistry	54
Biology & Biochemistry	50
Plant & Animal Science	49
Pharmacology & Toxicology	48
Agricultural Sciences	48
Geosciences	42
Materials Science	31
Immunology	25
Microbiology	20
Molecular Biology & Gene..	18
Physics	12
Mathematics	3

3) Do those leading institutions have services that respond to bibliometric needs? Is there a co-authorship of professionals specializing in bibliometrics?

Conclusions

- 1) The analyzed dataset has a high impact, given the constant increases in citations received, together with a high percentage of journals in quartiles 1 and 2.
- 2) Bibliometric analysis contribute mainly to Clinical Medicine, Environment/Ecology, Engineering and Psychiatry/Psychology, and their main identified thematic focuses.
- 3) There is a high presence of services and professionals specializing in bibliometrics in the leading detected institutions.

